

Sequence Clock: A Dynamic Resource Orchestrator for Serverless Architectures

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Abstract—Function-as-a-service (FaaS) represents the next frontier in the evolution of cloud computing being an emerging paradigm that removes the burden of configuration and management issues from users. This is achieved by replacing the well-established monolithic approach with graphs of standalone, small, stateless, event-driven components called functions. At the same time, from the cloud providers’ perspective, problems such as availability, load balancing and scalability need to be resolved without being aware of the functionality, behavior or resource requirements of their tenants’ code. However, in this context, functions’ containers coexist with others inside a host of finite resources, where a passive resource allocation technique does not guarantee a well-defined quality of service (QoS) in regards to time latency. In this paper, we present *Sequence Clock*, an expandable latency targeting tool that actively monitors serverless invocations in a cluster and offers execution of a sequential chain of functions, also known as pipelines or sequences, while achieving the targeted time latency. Two regulation methods were utilized, with one of them achieving up to 82% decrease in the severity of time violations and in some cases even eliminating them completely.

Index Terms—serverless computing, faas, QoS, OpenWhisk, Kubernetes

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, there is an ever-increasing number of workloads pushed and executed on the Cloud. As the competition gets increased and the Time-to-Market plays a significant role in software-oriented companies and startups, developers and engineers have become interested in solutions that would potentially decrease development time and allow them to focus on their application’s business logic. Over the years various cloud computing models have emerged offering different layers of abstraction and decoupling infrastructure maintenance from application development, i.e., Infrastructure-as-a-Service, Platform-as-a-Service, and now Function-as-a-Service. The latter is often used interchangeably with the term serverless computing, which is an emerging computing paradigm, also described as a whole new programming model [1]. Today several public cloud vendors already support serverless, e.g., AWS Lambda (Amazon) [2] and Google Cloud Functions [3], while the global market size of serverless is projected to triplicate by the end of 2025 [4].

Serverless could be defined as an emerging application deployment architecture that gets closer to the long-held promise of hiding server management from tenants [5]. The main idea of the Function-as-a-Service (FaaS) model, and the characteristic that defines serverless computing is the fact that a monolithic application should be decomposed and replaced

by a set of short-lived, stateless and event-driven functions. Each function is executed as a dedicated instance, usually a container, which provides a lightweight and isolated execution environment and runtime. Function’s ephemeral nature implies that it will be deployed whenever an invocation is requested and will be deleted right after handling the current request; thus eliminating the allocation of idle resources. Additionally, these functions need to call each other and share data in the process, resulting to the formation of graphs, which hereinafter are referred to as workflows or pipelines. Concerning the structure of these workflows, developers have the privilege to select from various options that are best-suited for each occasion. The simplest of all is sequential execution of functions, which can be presented as a list-like graph and be characterized as a sequence. As far as the execution runtime of a pipeline is concerned, whichever its structure may be, there are certain users’ configurations that include various allocation thresholds for computing resources, e.g., memory limit, number of processes, timeout, in the function level. Unfortunately, there is no guarantee for a certain execution latency concerning the overall workflow, which could also be interpreted as Quality-of-Service or QoS. Even if developers have found a tuned configuration according to which their function would behave in a predictable manner, e.g., terminates after *tms*, this analysis is insufficient. Each function instance coexists with a plethora of others and competes for the resources of the host; therefore, it is imposed resource interference resulting to unpredictable performance variability on runtime [6]. Having said that, for achieving QoS concerning a workflow’s tail latency, a more sophisticated runtime resource management system is required.

In this paper, i) we conduct a motivational analysis on Apache Openwhisk serverless platform, and identify a vast catalog of factors that may impact the end-to-end latency of a serverless pipeline. ii) We present Sequence Clock (SC) as a potential solution for QoS violations. We consider as QoS, a pre-defined execution time latency threshold of function sequences. SC is a distributed, latency targeting tool that actively monitors serverless invocations within a cluster and tries to regulate execution duration at sequence level. In its core, it includes two separate methods and levels of control. The first one is based on an unsupervised approach which experiences a notable and scalable functionality. The other one implements a greedy procedure for measuring the error (slack) from the target latency and uses a PID controller for estimating the required amount of CPU quotas, which

constitutes the tuning parameter. Moreover, a seemingly fair algorithm was developed for balancing resources between the containers placed on the same host. Overall, we achieve a decrease in the number of time violations and even a complete elimination of them in certain situations. In cases where the latter is not possible, we manage to lessen the severity of these violations.

II. RELATED WORK

Several works [5], [7], [8] have examined the implications of the serverless computing paradigm and proposed methodologies for evaluating the performance of serverless platforms. Accordingly, the problem of runtime resource management on serverless functions has attracted the interest of many research groups. Llama [9] is a heterogeneous serverless framework for auto-tuning video pipelines. By the time of writing this paper, it was the closest approach to ours as it also uses execution time latency as the target. In more depth, it calculates the target latency for each invocation of the pipeline and utilizes a cost optimizer in order to determine efficient configurations for each one of them. These configurations correspond to parameters such as the sampling rate, batch size, and the type of hardware, which can be tuned to meet the target latency while minimizing execution cost. FaastLane [10] does not offer a QoS constraint, but it tries to minimize workflow latency by eliminating function interaction and exchanges of data between them. Instead of executing each function in a separate, isolated container, it encapsulates the entire pipeline inside a single container instance. Functions are executed as threads within a single process, while data sharing is being replaced by simple load/store instructions. Other works, employ CPU cap control on Serverless functions with similar behavior, on single-node setup [11], or control theory to manage resources on geo-distributed edge nodes [12]. Unfortunately, while these approaches deliver some interesting results, they either lack in compatibility with existing serverless frameworks, or they are limited in specific applications. SC is a tool that can be currently integrated with Apache Openwhisk [13] and can be utilized for any kind of application and workload type.

III. MOTIVATION

A. Benchmarks Suites

In order to identify and analyze the problem of QoS violations in serverless pipelines, a series of different experiments were conducted for various stressing scenarios and configurations. For those, a suite of generic CPU intensive benchmarks was synthesized, while the third-party suite SeBS [14] has been also used. As the latter was developed targeting known platforms and not for OpenWhisk usage out of the box, a lot of effort has been put into converting the available functions into deployable components, compatible with the Openwhisk platform. More specifically, OpenWhisk uses pre-built images (with Alpine Linux as the final base image) that use version 3.6, 3.7 or 3.9 of Python with some common libraries, already installed into them. Whenever the usage of further external libraries is required, dependency issues will

rise. To overcome the above issue, a separate build of an image was performed with the existing runtime of Python *openwhisk/python3action* used as base for each function.

During the build process, full control over the installation of additional packages (Python modules or Alpine Linux Distribution’s packages) was achieved, with the desired data files stored inside each image whenever such thing was necessary. The final result is then deployed to OpenWhisk as a blackbox container. A unique ID is assigned to each function which is used later in the names of the constructed pipelines. For example, the sequence *p021* consists of the functions *uploader*, *compression*, *dynamic-html* with that particular order. Table I contains the ID of each function, where each function’s functionality is self explanatory.

As far as the generic benchmarks are concerned, their creation was crucial for the impact of CPU saturation to appear on the conducted experiments. Each one of them requires the minimum amount of all the other computational resources, i.e., memory, I/O, cold storage usage, and network. In more depth, six generic Python functions have been implemented from scratch with a structure similar to Algorithm 1.

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TABLE I: SeBS Actions IDs

ID	Function
0	uploader
1	dynamic-html
2	compression
3	graph-pagerank
4	graph-mst
5	graph-bfs
6	dnvisualization
7	videoprocessing
8	thumbnailer
9	sleep

Algorithm 1 Generic CPU intensive Action

```

1:  $i \leftarrow 0$ 
2:  $I \leftarrow 4$ 
3:  $N \leftarrow 1000000$ 
4: while  $i \neq I$  do
5:    $foo \leftarrow randomNumber()$ 
6:    $n \leftarrow 0$ 
7:   while  $n \neq N$  do
8:      $foo \leftarrow randomMathExpression(foo)$ 
9:      $n \leftarrow n + 1$ 
10:  end while
11:   $i \leftarrow i + 1$ 
12: end while

```

Each function consists of two nested for-loops with the outer one having a constant iteration number of four and the inner part computing mathematical expressions over the same variable. The actual expressions (line 7) and the result do not matter, thus by trying various combinations additional actions can be produced. Furthermore, sequential nested for-loops and a lightweight mathematical operation into the final loop (a simple addition) may result into similar behaviour. As far as the constant outer loop pattern in every action is concerned, it was placed strategically in order to explore the behaviour of multi-threaded & multi-processed applications¹.

¹The maximum core count per node in the cluster was four.

While the aforementioned functions are single threaded applications by default, each iteration can be distributed to a single separated thread or process by leveraging the *multiprocessing* and the *threading* Python modules. It is also worth mentioning that by leveraging threads, the operation will not be executed in parallel but concurrently. In contrast, the *multiprocessing* module offers the usage of separate processes, which utilize more than one CPU cores as they try to get executed in parallel.

Pipelines with length of three and six functions, were produced with the names *stg3*, *stg6*, *mtg3*, *mtg6*, *mpg3*, and *mpg6*. The *st* prefix is used for single threaded pipelines, the *mt* prefix for the multi-threaded pipelines and the *mp* for the multi-process ones respectively.

B. Experimental Infrastructure

For the rest of the paper, we consider a cluster of four virtual machines, deployed on a set of physical servers. In each one of them Ubuntu 20.04 LTS with 5.4 version of the Linux Kernel is installed as the operating system. Our cluster is managed by Kubernetes [15] (K8s), which represents the de facto standard for the life-cycle management of containers. The first of these four nodes is used as the Kubernetes master node component, while the others are considered as workers. On top of Kubernetes, we have installed Openwhisk, which is compatible and exploits the Kubernetes scheduler for the orchestration of functions. At the same time, we have labeled each worker node with a *openwhisk - role = invoker* tag, to indicate the nodes responsible for executing the post-invocation actions, which would be executed on the Invoker component of the default Openwhisk implementation. All the workers have the same amount of memory equal to 15.6 GiB, while we opted for some diversity on CPU core count as the controlling parameter was based on it. The high ratio between system memory and CPU cores allowed the deployment & the invocation of several function containers within the cluster, avoiding RAM shortages or cold starts.

As far as OpenWhisk deployment is concerned *KubernetesContainerFactory* was selected as it provides more control over functions' containers compared with the *DockerContainerFactory* option. The available user memory was set at 34.8 GiB, which allowed for 4 GiB of free memory in each node. Various limits, i.e., individual action concurrency, number of invocations per minute, and number of concurrent invocations were increased, while at the same time *persistence* was enabled. The latter has been achieved by deploying a separate Network File System (NFS) server in the cluster (specifically into master node), which manages automatic Persistent Volumes' creation. This configuration choice was vital as it permitted data preservation during node failures/restarts preventing from the complete loss of application state or the need for OpenWhisk Helm Chart re-installation.

C. Observing Target Latency

In the following lines, we try to investigate various reasons that may lead a serverless sequence to time violations and to

clarify the importance and the complexity of this subject.

1) *Impact of Resource Contention*: Function containers, that coexist in the same host machine, compete for various resources. These might be the network, the time in the CPU, I/O, system memory etc. Moreover, the more resource types a function needs the more severe and noticeable the impact will be on the function's performance degradation. This effect becomes even worse on sequences of functions, in which the latency stacks up.

The behaviour of the end-to-end latency in regards to a quantity that represents the cluster's pressure, indicates that this phenomenon is present and important even in well-designed and widely-used frameworks like OpenWhisk. For instance, in Fig. 1b the end-to-end latency of the pipeline *p024879* as a function of rps values is plotted (the distribution of latency is illustrated with the usage of boxplots). Each invocation uses a different set of containers in order to imitate resource contention of independent tenants' sequences with similar footprint. This was made possible by using different aliases for both the sequences and the internal functions, for OpenWhisk to consider them as non-identical.

From this result, two points can be figured out. First of all, it is clear that higher rps levels lead to higher values for end-to-end latency. In fact, for this pipeline, which depends on various system resources, the increase is exponential. Secondly, there is not only a mean level increase of the depending variable, but also an increase of the variance of each distribution. That means, that not only a sequence gets delayed when more pressure is applied to the system, but also the time latency becomes unpredictable.

2) *CPU Saturation*: To make things worse, during our experiments we observe similar behaviour even for generic, CPU-bound benchmarks. In Fig. 1c, the results of the sequence *stg6* are illustrated for the same experiment. In this case, CPU saturation is one of the main reasons (others are network delay, OpenWhisk's queuing inside invokers etc.) provoking this behaviour. In particular, the cluster offers 10 cores in total, i.e., two nodes with 4 cores and one with 2 cores, which (given the total number of invocations that take place during this experiment) implies that there is an amount of time where the total number of containers requiring a CPU is greater than the cluster's total capacity.

3) *Impact of Cold Starts*: The concept of *cold starts* [7] refers to the phenomenon according to which a function invocation occurs with no available container present inside the cluster. In such case, for the action to be executed, a new container is spawned, adding a delay to the total execution time (the opposite concept is called *warm start*). A way to test the severity of this delay and its variations depending on system's state is to repeat the previous experiment and make sure that each function invocation suffers from a cold start. In Fig. 1a, it is clear that such a decision affects notably the time latency of the pipeline. The related quantity increases exponentially and more drastically in contrast to the case of warm starts

Fig. 1: Factors of pipelines' latency violations

(a) Abstract Representation of Slack.

(b) Abstract Representation of a target latency PID Controller

Fig. 2: Abstract Representation of slack quantity and a regulation mechanism proposal.

4) *Impact of Concurrency & Queuing Phenomena:* Concurrency in actions is a complicated subject, which is handled with various techniques by each framework. In OpenWhisk, by default, each deployed pod/container is able to handle only one request at a time. If an invocation of the same action is triggered before the termination of the running one, OpenWhisk will spawn a new pod/container resulting to a *cold start*. There is an option for increasing concurrency capabilities of a function, but one should easily understand that as resource contention is a concept to worry about in the node level, the same applies in the container level ².

By conducting the already described experiment of sequential invocations of variable rps levels, while forcing each function to reuse the container of previous invocations, we observe a behaviour like the one in Fig. 1d. End-to-end latency is plotted as a function of the time of invocation for various rps values. Normally, a bell-like curve is expected and yet a linear causality appears. Consequently, in cases where OpenWhisk's runtime does not truly support concurrent invocations, even if the latter is enabled, a queuing effect will rise ³.

5) *CPU Quotas Affection:* An additional factor that has an influence on target latency is how much time a function, i.e., a container, is allowed to use the host's CPU. A way to quantify this concept is through CPU quotas. In order to explore the affection of this metric to pipelines' latency, we conduct a single invocation of a pipeline with various values of CPU quotas (various percentages of the default CPU period of 100000ms) of the related Docker container. The common response of the end-to-end latency for these CPU quotas levels is shown in Fig. 3.

²This issue is present in NodeJS *pre-warm* containers, which are not coupled with any action and remain deployed even after termination [16].

³Python's runtime is implemented using an old version of Flask framework, which does not support concurrent requests.

It is clear that with values less than 80% of a single CPU, function's execution time starts to decelerate drastically. In addition, as this specific action does not leverage multiple cores, after 100% of the available CPU period the effects of quotas increase start to fade out. This behaviour motivates us to utilize CPU quotas as a tuning parameter within Sequence Clock.

Fig. 3: CPU Quotas affection on function time latency.

IV. SEQUENCE CLOCK

A. Mathematical Modeling & Problem Definition

Before moving on with our proposal, it is worth mentioning some basic mathematical definitions and concepts that formulate our problem, alongside with some conventions that will be made in the rest of this paper.

1) *General Definitions:* Let l be the targeted time latency of a sequence s of n serverless functions f_0, f_1, \dots, f_{n-1} . During an invocation I , the measured execution time of function f_i is t_i for all $i, 0 \leq i < n$. We assert that the sequence s did not meet the target latency l , or violated the targeted latency l , or that a QoS violation occurred when:

$$T_I(s) = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} t_i > l \text{ for the invocation } I \quad (1)$$

Otherwise, we deem that sequence s met the targeted latency l . In case of a QoS violation, we call the quantity $\frac{T_I(s)-l}{l}$ violation factor, which can be used as an indicator of the severity of each violation.

For a given experiment I of this sequence s with target latency l , let t_i be the measured execution time of function f_i with $0 \leq i < n$. If we know that each function f_i should run under τ_i time, with $\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \tau_i = l$, we define slack in (2).

$$slack_i = slack_{f_i} = \sum_{j=0}^{i-1} \tau_j - \sum_{k=0}^{i-1} t_k = \sum_{j=0}^{i-1} (\tau_j - t_j) \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) holds true for f_i $1 \leq i < n$, while it is safe to assume in most cases that $slack_0 = slack(f_0) = 0$. In general, as Figure 2a shows, should $slack_i$ be greater than zero, sequence execution is ahead of the target latency before the execution of function f_i starts. Otherwise, sequence execution is behind the target latency. Basically, $slack$ is current state's error, which can be utilized by a feedback loop, like the one in Figure 2b, as a regulation mechanism of target latency.

2) *Problems' Definition*: The QoS problem is defined as follows. For any set of m invocations I_0, I_1, \dots, I_{m-1} we try to minimize the number $N_{violation} \leq m$ of the times that sequence s violated the target latency l . Equivalently, we try to maximize the quantity $m - N_{violation}$. Another problem concerning the QoS is the following. For any set of m invocations I_0, I_1, \dots, I_{m-1} and for any violation of s we try to minimize the *violation factor*. The above two problems are not equivalent, but a well behaved resource management system should target both of them.

B. Sequence Clock's Design

Sequence Clock (SC) is a distributed system, which consists of three different components, i.e., *Deployer*, *Watcher Supreme*, and *Watcher/s*. Each one of them is considered as a Kubernetes resource and exists inside the cluster independently. In addition there is also another element called *Sequence Controller*, which leverages OpenWhisk by being a serverless action by itself and being mapped to a unique serverless sequence. An abstract representation of the entire stack is given in Figure 4. The entire code for Sequence Clock is available on Github⁴.

In a nutshell, SC (*Sequence Controller*) deploys each controlled sequence (marked as orange circles), as an OpenWhisk action, whose only purpose is to invoke (Figure 4: 1b) each function (marked as yellow circles) of the pipeline with the proper order and gather metrics. The same component, during pipeline execution, communicates (Figure 4: 1a) with the centralized service of *Watcher Supreme*, to whom it sends requests for resource allocation. The latter transfers these requests (Figure 4: 2a, 2b) to the *Watchers*, which are deployed in each node and they are responsible for managing and distributing computing resources in the node level as fair as possible. Each *Watcher*, depending on the received requests, offers further computing capacity to containers of sequences with negative slack, while it reduces the same quantity in containers of sequences with positive slack. The regulated parameter that was used is CPU Quotas, as its effects on containers' performance were studied extensively.

Fig. 4: Sequence Clock Architecture

In more depth, the *Deployer* is a simple component that aims to automate the sequence creation and deployment by offering a simple API to developers. The *Watcher Supreme* acts as the entypoint of *Sequence Controllers* to node *Watchers*. Instead of pinging each node separately for the aforementioned requests, the *Sequence Controller* communicates asynchronously with only one component, i.e., the *Watcher Supreme*. The latter has the responsibility to find in which node a function's container is or will be placed. When it obtains this information, i.e., when a node replies positively, the specified component transfers the resource allocation request to the associated *Watcher*, for the regulation to be initiated.

As far as the *Sequence Controller* is concerned, it is a separate serverless function mapped to a specific sequence. Its only purpose is to invoke each action and transfer its output to the next one. This process summarizes the functionality of the unsupervised/dummy *Sequence Controller*, shown in Algorithm 2, which lets the internal actions to be executed in a best effort policy. This simple, yet powerful, approach can

Algorithm 2 Unsupervised (Dummy) Sequence Controller

```

1: function DUMMY(args)
2:   res ← args
3:   for f in functions do
4:     res ← invoke(f,res)
5:   end for
6:   return res
7: end function

```

be easily expanded and introduce several methods of dynamic resource allocation. The one, that we opted for, is the *greedy* Algorithm (3) that evaluates the present, future, and past state of the pipeline and tries to achieve the desired latency with the exploitation of a PID controller. It is characterized by the term *greedy*, as it tries to regulate the system by correcting only the resources of the currently running function. The above is made possible by computing the *slack* value of each function (line 14), as it was defined in (2), as well as by gathering other metrics like the sum of previous *slacks* (line 15) and the *slack* of the previous function (line 13). All these measurements

⁴<https://github.com/john98nf/SequenceClock.git>

are then sent to the *Watcher Supreme* (line 8), in order for the regulation mechanism to get initiated. After the termination of function execution a *reset* request is sent back to the *Watcher Supreme* for the related resources to get unbound (line 10).

Algorithm 3 Greedy Sequence Controller

```

1: function GREEDY(args)
2:   res ← args
3:   slack ← 0
4:   sum ← 0                                     ▷ Sum of slacks
5:   previous ← 0                               ▷ Previous Slack
6:   for f in functions do
7:     t_start ← now()
8:     requestToWatchers(slack, previous, sum)
9:     res ← invoke(f, res)
10:    resetWatchers()
11:    t_end ← now()
12:    actual ← t_end - t_start                   ▷ Actual elapsed time
13:    previous ← slack
14:    slack ← slack + profiledTime(f) - actual
15:    sum ← sum + slack
16:  end for
17:  return res
18: end function

```

Last but not least, it is worth mentioning the structure of the *Watcher/s*, which are the main component/s of the system, when *Greedy Sequence Controllers* are being used. Exactly one *Watcher* is deployed inside each invoker node with the responsibility of balancing computing resources of each node and regulating sequences' time latency based on the metrics, that it receives. Figure 5 presents its internal structure and explains its functionality with a simple example of resource request handling. The entire mechanism is initiated with the incoming request, which is transferred from the *Watcher's* server to the internal component called *Conflict Resolver*. The latter checks the local data structure, *Registry*, and the local Docker runtime for the related function container. If such a runtime is present, the PID controller computes the desired CPU Quotas, which will potentially be provided to the related container by the *Conflict Resolver* with respect to the available CPU resources.

In order for the *Conflict Resolver* to distribute fairly the available CPU Quotas of the host machine, it offers each action container a multiple of the desired amount of CPU Quotas by a λ factor. Its value is being computed by the formula in (3), where T represents the default CPU period, N_{cores} the node core count, n the number of resource requests handled by this node, and r_i the desired CPU Quotas for each $0 \leq i \leq n - 1$ request.

$$\lambda = \frac{N_{cores} \cdot T}{\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} r_i} \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) is used when $\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} r_i > N_{cores} \cdot T$, a situation which could be described by the term *saturation*. Otherwise, a value of one can be safely assigned to factor λ . Furthermore, the exhaustive computation of the summation term can be

Fig. 5: Watcher's Workflow

easily avoided with the usage of the recursive formula:

$$\lambda_{new} = \frac{N_{cores} \cdot T \cdot \lambda_{old}}{N_{cores} \cdot T + (r_{new} - r_{old}) \cdot \lambda_{old}} \quad (4)$$

, where r_{new} and r_{old} represent the new and old values of CPU Quotas respectively, concerning the container of interest.

The physical meaning of 3 and 4 is that in case of resource contention/saturation, i.e., in case that the functions' containers require a higher amount of CPU quotas (according to *PID Controller's* output) than the available, each one of them will be provided with a percentage of the requested physical quantity. In addition, in each node the lambda factor lets the ratio between the quotas of two functions untouched, meaning that actions with negative slack will still be provided with higher resources than the ones with positive or less (by absolute value) slack.

Finally it should be pointed out that the entire structure of the *Watcher/s* was designed with the principle that each user action invocation results to one pod/container inside the cluster. Such thing is not entirely true, as OpenWhisk will try to scale out and spawn more containers if the invocation rate is high, i.e., higher than the execution rate with concurrency of the function being equal to one. Fortunately, if one enables concurrency in such actions, the above statement corresponds to reality.

V. EVALUATION

In this section, we evaluate the performance of our proposed system in various scenarios, where we compare both the unsupervised (*Dummy*) and the *Greedy* version of SC with the default OpenWhisk's pipelines. A way to quantify these stressing scenarios or the levels of system's pressure, is to experiment with different values of the requests/invocations per second metric, i.e., to perform sequential invocations of a pipeline with a constant rate rps or equivalently with a constant time difference $\Delta t = \frac{1}{rps}$. The default experiment interval for each rps level is set to 120 seconds, while rps values fluctuate between 0.1 and 0.5 with an approximate step of 0.15.

For eliminating queuing phenomena and time violations due to *cold starts*, we need to have complete control over the way each function invocation is being executed, i.e., by which container each request is being handled. Thus, during the experimentation, each function is deployed inside OpenWhisk with an additional ID or alias in order for each invocation to be distinguishable from others of the same function of the same pipeline. This approach guarantees that every request is placed on a separate container. Moreover, the execution of some initial calls ensures that all the necessary containers are deployed inside the cluster in advance, avoiding *cold starts*' aftereffects.

A. Pipeline Profiling & Target Latency Extraction

As far as the profiling process of each pipeline is concerned, we avoided using the time observed during the execution of the pipeline in isolation, as a reference point. The reason is that it would be impossible to achieve that kind of QoS, as it is unlikely for such sequences to run under those circumstances. Thus, a similar method with the one proposed in [17] is performed. In more depth, we set the target latency for each pipeline as the 99-th percentile latency of the knee of the related plot, where the application experiences a rapid increase in tail latency after exceeding a load threshold (typically between 0.2 ~ 0.4 *rps*).

Fig. 6: OpenWhisk: Target Latency Extraction from the 99th-percentile.

For automating the knee location detection for each plot we utilize the *kneed* Python module [18], which is based on the findings of [19]. Whenever this algorithm is not capable of locating such a point, e.g., when the latency experiences linear instead of exponential increase, we perform a linear search to find at which point the growth between each value and the next one is higher than a certain percentage relative to the original value. For instance, in Figure 6 one can observe the knee of the sequence *stg6* to appear at 0.33 of *rps* resulting to a target latency of 26956 ms.

B. Comparing Sequence Clock with OpenWhisk

In the following lines, an in depth study for the behaviour of Sequence Clock and its two algorithms in comparison with OpenWhisk is presented. For our analysis, we perform a plethora of tests by utilizing the pipelines *stg3*, *stg6*, *mtg3*, *mtg6*, *mpg3*, *mpg6* from the generic suite and *p021*, *p643*, *p024879*, *p051463* created using the SeB Suite. However, as performance is similar among pipelines with minor differences, Figure 7 includes the observations of *stg6*, *mtg3*, and *p643*.

Starting off with *stg6* with a target latency of 31064ms, one can conclude that the mechanism of *Sequence Controllers* does

not result to any additional network delay as Dummy algorithm's performance indicates in Figures 7a, 7b. Furthermore, the *Greedy* algorithm and the PID controller result in a 99-th percentile of time latency to be extremely near target latency for *rps* values that are less than 0.33 Hz. Unfortunately, for higher values, SC not only fails to regulate the specified quantity but ends up to be worse than the default configuration of OpenWhisk. The above arguments are also confirmed by Figure 7b, where Sequence Clock seems to be more stable than OpenWhisk for the values that it achieves a time latency with a distribution near the target. In addition, in Figure 7c Sequence Clock appears to have the highest violations' percentage for all *rps* levels. For the values that are beneath 0.33, as the boxplot in 7b and Figure 8a imply, these violations are not severe. However, OpenWhisk originally never had violations in these levels of system's pressure.

Moving on with *mtg3* with a target latency equal to 12526ms, it is clear that sequences with less functions suffer less from latency elongation, as violations' percentages in Figure 7f from OpenWhisk remain below 20% for all *rps* levels. Furthermore, Figure 7d reveals that the PID controller's gains cannot be optimized and tuned for all the pipelines, regardless their structure and inner functions, as the values that resulted in successful regulation in *stg6*, now result into a steady state error in *mtg3*. As far as violations are concerned, the situation is even worse than *stg6* as both the violation factor and violations' percentage remain high for all the *rps* levels.

Similar behaviour is observed in more realistic sequences like pipeline *p643* with a target latency of 6023ms. Pipelines with 3-function length do not achieve the desired time latency and lead the system to violations as Figure 7i illustrates, while the steady state error reappears, with the PID controller functions as un-optimised and un-tuned component in Figures 7g, 7i.

VI. DISCUSSION

A. Causes of Failure

It is really important to look for the reasons that have led *Greedy* Sequence Clock to perform significantly worse than OpenWhisk. First of all, we should point out that measurements showed that time latency many times behaved like a random variable, especially in high levels of *rps*. We emphasize that every form of conventional regulation (resembling the CPU quotas PID controller) will lead to a shift to distribution's mean and a scaling to distribution's variance. Thus, violations will appear even in situations, where they were absent, i.e., during lower values of *rps*. This would not have been a problem in SC's case, if these violations had remained between a reasonable interval (e.g., with a violation factor less than 0.1) and a reasonable percentage.

The real problem becomes clear when studying the behaviour presented in Figure 7a. Latency suffers from deceleration during *rps* levels that are higher than the value which specified each target. For example, target latency for the pipeline *stg6* was set as the 99-th percentile of the latency

Fig. 7: OpenWhisk vs Unsupervised/Dummy SC vs Sequence Clock.

distribution during $rps = 0.33$, while SC seems to function worse for $rps > 0.33$. The reason behind this is the fact that while quotas changes seem to achieve a descent result in decelerating actions, they fail at accelerating them. As CPU Quotas indicate the amount on the CPU during a certain CPU period, a quantity larger than that will remain unexploited by the specified action, if this action does not have a need of that extra time.

Additionally, Sequence Clock is built with the ambition of trying to regulate action sequences without a prior knowledge of the functions' code. This results the PID controller to perform as expected for certain pipelines and behave as non-optimized for others. To put it simply, the gains which result to a responsive system for 6-function pipelines, at the same time lead 3-function pipelines to a shifted latency distribution with action execution ending before slack settles into the desired value of zero. Other pipelines ended up with a latency that had a mean value near the desired one, but appeared with large values of variance, which implies less stability.

B. Dummy SC Superiority Paradox

In Figures 7c, 9b, and 9d, an unexpected characteristic of Sequence Clock can be noticed. The *Unsupervised/Dummy* Sequence Clock performs better than OpenWhisk not only

concerning time latency, as it suffers from less violations, but also concerning the violation factor density which is closer to zero. The latter means that in cases, where the percentage of violations is similar to the one of OpenWhisk, these violations are less severe.

At this point an explanation is desirable on how an unsupervised system handles invocations in high pressure situations better than the supervised proposal and the default configuration of OpenWhisk. To begin with, superiority over the *Greedy* algorithm of Sequence Clock is explained by the aforementioned arguments of Sec. VI-A. However, this does not still provide a solid answer on the outperformance over OpenWhisk. OpenWhisk handles sequences' invocation in a centralized way. No external separate component is deployed inside the cluster with the purpose of orchestrating invocations of a running pipeline. On the contrary, Sequence Clock and thus *Unsupervised/Dummy* Sequence Clock, deploys a separate action for this purpose and thus a separate pod/container inside the cluster. This decentralized way of invoking the internal functions of a pipeline offers more scalability and achieves both goals mentioned in Sec. IV-A. Moreover, if we accept the above argument as true, then we can also explain the absence of network delay in *Sequence Controllers*' execution

Fig. 8: OpenWhisk vs Unsupervised/Dummy SC vs Sequence Clock: Distribution of Violation Factor

Fig. 9: OpenWhisk vs Unsupervised/Dummy SC vs Sequence Clock: Distribution of Violation Factor

even with the additional transfer of data from an action to another. This approach is not network optimised, as these components need to fetch each function's output and redirect it to the next function as input⁵. Yet, the absence of such a component in OpenWhisk's sequences indicates that a similar process occurs.

In any case, data showed that if cluster nodes are utilized with a more intuitive way, scalability and stability can be increased. For instance, in *stg3* pipeline's experiment Dummy SC suffers from approximately the same amount of violations' percentages (Figure 9a). However, it manages to maintain the violation factor lower than the values that OpenWhisk allows,

⁵For a sequence s of n functions f_0, f_1, \dots, f_{n-1} , *Dummy Sequence Controller* performs $2n + 2$ data transfers (including initial input and final output), while the actual needed data transfers are n .

with a decrease by a 82% factor as shown in Figure 9b. In more realistic sequences of higher length, e.g., pipeline *p024879*, the maximum of violation factor's distribution (ignoring the three outliers) shifts by a factor of 73% (it drops from ~ 10 to ~ 6) (Figure 9d) and the total percentage of violations is less comparing to OpenWhisk (Figure 9c).

VII. CONCLUSIONS

A. Summary

The challenge of offering Quality of Service (QoS) in Serverless architectures was studied extensively. Time latency constrains for serverless pipelines until today remain a challenge not extensively explored by Cloud providers and open-source frameworks. Attempting to observe the outcomes of this problem, we performed a plethora of experiments at

function and at sequence level by testing their performance through a variety of different variables and configurations. We identified a vast catalog of factors that have an impact on the pipeline’s end-to-end latency and we concentrated on resource contention and system’s pressure. The experiments showed, on average, an almost exponential growth in the latency of a pipeline when plotted against increasing invocation rates, with the stability and predictability of the system getting vastly decreased, as well. These observations make clear the necessity for a dynamic runtime resource management system in serverless platforms.

Additionally, we designed and implemented Sequence Clock, a target latency tool for serverless pipelines, which tries to distribute fairly CPU resources into the hosted actions’ containers of each node. Both the *Greedy* and the *Unsupervised/Dummy* version of SC were evaluated on a set of runs, where the cluster was set under various stress conditions of increasing rate of invocations. We evaluated the capability of Sequence Clock’s control loop to decelerate serverless pipelines and to achieve in certain situations more stable distributions of end-to-end latency near the specified target. The inability of *Greedy* SC to reduce time violations’ percentages and to confine the severity of these violations was also shown by the detailed analysis of system’s metrics. However, the same experiments indicated that *Unsupervised* Sequence Clock, a distributed and simpler approach was able to achieve the same or even better results than OpenWhisk. The percentage of violations was reduced (in some cases even down to zero) and the maximum of violation factor was decreased up to 82% for 3-function pipelines and up to 73% for 6-function pipelines. Finally, an exhaustive explanation was provided on the reasons that led Sequence Clock into this underperforming behaviour, whenever the CPU quotas control is enabled and its unexpected superiority over OpenWhisk with the usage of the dummy mode.

B. Future Work

As far as Sequence Clock and its regulation mechanism based on CPU quotas are concerned, an interesting approach would be a combination of the *Greedy* algorithm and the *Unsupervised/Dummy* method, where a configuration of the *Watchers* will use CPU quotas regulation for decelerating pipelines, while in high contention situations it will let the function containers to run uncontrollably. Although the latter modification might offer further information into the phenomenon of time violations, a more crucial concept should be studied and that is the parameters and configurations that could result in an actual function’s latency decrease. Had these variables been found, it would set the foundations for future systems that could try to dynamically distribute, allocate or control system’s resources for achieving the desirable result.

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